

VoEvol – D3 –

A Report on Modern Evolutionary Methods for Quality-driven Optimization in Information Visualization, Image Processing and Design Problems

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 951911

info@ai4media.eu

www.ai4media.eu

Index of Contents

Index of Contents	2
1 Introduction	3
2 Advantages of Evolutionary Methods.....	4
3 Single- and Multi-objective Methods.....	6
4 Quality-Diversity Methods	12
5 Summary of Presented Work	18
6 Conclusions	23
7 References.....	24

1 Introduction

Evolutionary optimization is an important part of the VolEvol pipeline, as it is responsible for automating the search and rendering processes which generate resulting images of the volume data set. The learning component of the VolEvol project makes use of an evolutionary optimizer which searches through the space of renderer inputs. These inputs are sets of parameters used by the volume renderer to generate images of the volume data set. Examples of such parameters are color values, opacities, and viewing directions. Searching through this parameter space becomes a complex task when the mapping of data values from the volume dataset to visual properties is achieved using a complicated function with multiple parameters and control points. The optimization objectives, formed from quality descriptors, are also a factor which increases the complexity of the problem. Finding parameter sets which result in meaningful representations of volume data is therefore challenging to formulate as an optimization problem. Consequently, in order to automate the VolEvol pipeline, we rely on evolutionary optimizers to find the parameter values which eventually result in useful representations of the volume data sets. Aside from the fact that this is one of the key aspects of the project objectives (i.e., using evolutionary learning), evolutionary methods are diverse and especially highly configurable. For any basic evolutionary algorithm there may exist multiple variations, modifications and improvements. More importantly, the parameters of such an approach often play a significant role in convergence speed, the amount that the objective is minimized/maximized, variations and diversity within the population across generations etc. An example in this regard would be the mutation probability in a genetic algorithm. Higher mutation rates may improve the coverage of the solution space and increase the chance of finding a global maximum, at the expense of convergence speed and possibly introducing too much randomness into the population. Finding the right optimizer is a multi-task approach which involves adjusting the parameters of the method and correctly defining the optimization objective(s). Quality-diversity algorithms add the challenge of defining the feature space and the subdivision method.

In learning how to work with evolutionary optimizers for the objectives of VolEvol, the project team relies on previous experience using evolutionary optimization, as well as a study of existing related work. Consequently, our research and documentation efforts involved searching and analysing the related literature for existing applications of evolutionary algorithms for quality-oriented optimization. In this report, we present our findings in terms of some of the relevant results from the available scientific literature, considering the topic of the project. We mainly divide the results into two broad categories: classic single- and multi-objective optimization, and quality-diversity (QD) methods. Considering the objectives of VolEvol, the two categories are significantly different, mostly due to the fact that QD methods have in-built mechanisms for generating diverse solution sets. While we mostly focus on evolutionary optimization applied in visualization and image-processing, we also present some results from other fields which we considered relevant.

2 Advantages of Evolutionary Methods

This section serves to reinforce our motivation for using evolutionary learning, aside from it simply being a requirement outlined in the project objectives. Evolutionary optimization is a powerful and versatile approach used to solve complex optimization problems inspired by the principles of biological evolution. Evolutionary methods draw upon the mechanisms of natural selection, reproduction, mutation, and survival of the fittest to iteratively search for optimal solutions within a predefined search space. Evolutionary optimization algorithms, such as genetic algorithms, evolutionary strategies, and genetic programming, have gained popularity in various fields due to their ability to address a wide range of optimization challenges.

Evolutionary optimization is robust in handling noisy and complex objective functions. It doesn't require gradient information, making it suitable for problems with discontinuous, non-differentiable, or non-convex search spaces. This robustness allows it to explore a broader range of solutions and escape local optima. Unlike gradient-based methods, which are prone to getting stuck in local optima, evolutionary algorithms maintain diversity within the population, ensuring that they continue to explore the search space for potentially better solutions. Additionally, evolutionary optimization can be easily parallelized, making it suitable for high-performance computing environments. Multiple candidate solutions can evolve independently within the same generation, speeding up the optimization process for problems with a large number of decision variables or computationally-expensive objective functions.

Evolutionary algorithms can adapt to changing problem landscapes and dynamically adjust their exploration-exploitation strategies. This adaptability is particularly valuable in optimization scenarios where the problem characteristics may vary over time. Where multiple objectives are concerned, evolutionary methods easily extend to multi-objective optimization problems. They can generate a diverse set of Pareto-optimal solutions that represent trade-offs between conflicting objectives, enabling decision-makers to make informed choices. The adaptability of evolutionary methods also resides in the fact that, unlike many optimization techniques that rely on specific mathematical models or assumptions about the problem structure, evolutionary optimization approaches are model-free. They do not require prior knowledge of the problem, making them suitable for a wide range of real-world applications. Additionally, evolutionary algorithms are highly customizable. Various aspects of such algorithms may be tailored, such as selection mechanisms, crossover and mutation operators, and population sizes, to suit the characteristics of the specific problem at hand. When adjusting the parameters of such a method, the general idea is to strike a balance between exploration (discovering new solutions) and exploitation (refining promising solutions), which helps explore complex solution spaces.

Evolutionary optimization methods have proven to be versatile tools with applications spanning various domains, including information visualization and image processing. These techniques, inspired by the principles of natural selection, offer unique advantages in solving complex optimization problems in these fields. In information visualization, evolutionary algorithms are useful in solving a wide array of issues. They aid in optimizing the layout of visual elements, ensuring that complex data can be more easily comprehended. For applications such as arranging nodes in network graphs or positioning data points in scatterplots, evolutionary

methods help strike a balance between clarity and minimizing visual clutter. Feature selection, particularly in high-dimensional datasets, benefits from evolutionary algorithms. These techniques efficiently navigate expansive feature spaces, pinpointing subsets that best convey the data's essence, facilitating better visualization. Color mapping, vital for conveying information effectively, is also an area where evolution comes into play. Evolutionary optimization ensures that color schemes are not only aesthetically pleasing but also perceptually distinct and accessible to all users, including those with color vision deficiencies. Managing the visual hierarchy is another application area. Evolutionary optimization helps designers determine how to represent complex data structures, ensuring that important information is prominently displayed in visualizations like treemaps or sunburst diagrams. Cluster visualization, used for identifying patterns within data, can be enhanced with evolutionary methods. These techniques assist in discovering optimal cluster representations, simplifying interpretation.

In the domain of image processing, evolutionary optimization techniques provide invaluable support: image enhancement, which involves modifying attributes like brightness, contrast, and sharpness, benefits from evolutionary algorithms. These algorithms adaptively adjust image parameters, improving overall quality and visual appeal. Image registration, critical in medical imaging and remote sensing, employs evolutionary optimization to align multiple images precisely. This alignment aids in more accurate analysis and diagnosis. Image segmentation, the process of partitioning images into meaningful regions, is optimized using evolutionary algorithms. These techniques improve the accuracy of segmenting objects or regions of interest, enhancing image analysis. Image reconstruction in fields such as computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is optimized through evolutionary methods. This results in reduced artifacts and superior image quality, essential for accurate diagnosis. Image compression techniques can be optimized with evolutionary algorithms, reducing file sizes while preserving essential details. This is particularly beneficial for applications with limited storage or bandwidth. Object detection and recognition models also benefit from evolutionary optimization. Algorithms tuned through evolutionary processes lead to better accuracy in tasks such as facial recognition or object tracking.

In both information visualization and image processing, evolutionary optimization methods excel in handling high-dimensional and nonlinear optimization problems. Their adaptability to changing data and ability to explore diverse solutions make them useful tools for enhancing the quality and effectiveness of visualizations and image processing tasks. Particularly with regard to quality and diversity optimization, evolutionary learning can be an effective tool for searching through the complex solution spaces often encountered in such instances. QD algorithms in particular excel at solving the quality-diversity problem due to their inbuilt means of seeking diversity, albeit at the expense of requiring the definition of a feature space, in addition to the solution space normally associated with conventional optimizers. As we develop the VolEvol project, we continue to perfect our understanding of these methods and their use in fulfilling the project objectives.

3 Single- and Multi-objective Methods

In this section we describe some of the more relevant related work with regard to “traditional” optimization. We differentiate conventional optimizers which operate directly on the solution space of the problem from QD algorithms, which are discussed in a subsequent section. Since our analysis of the results from the related literature indicates that most authors formulate their work as a single-optimization problem, with multi-optimization methods representing a restricted minority, we decided to group these two approaches within the same section.

Conventional single optimization evolutionary methods formulate their objective as a single function, to be either minimized or maximized. In genetic optimization, such a function is also referred to as the “fitness” function, and it serves to indicate the usefulness of any particular solution. Consequently, the choice of the objective function is crucial to the success of the optimizer. Such an optimizer converges toward the “best” solution, which is considered to be the one with the best fitness, i.e. the values of the input value vector which minimize/maximize the objective function. In multi-optimization, multiple objectives are considered, some of which need to be minimized/maximized. In such scenarios, the “best” solution is difficult to define, as it is common for multiple objectives to evolve in contrary directions. Minimizing one objective function may lead to maximizing the other. Therefore, optimal solutions are identified as part of the Pareto front of the solution space, i.e. the set of solutions which offer the best compromises in terms of achieving all objectives. The solutions considered to be the most useful are commonly chosen from this front, requiring criteria outside of the optimizer for their selection. Various methods have been proposed in the related literature in terms of using evolutionary optimizers for analysing, measuring and ensuring quality in image processing, visualization and related fields. In nearly all scenarios, the most commonly faced issues are, on the one hand, establishing criteria and metrics to be used as optimization objectives and, on the other hand, developing, customizing and tweaking an evolutionary method in order to ensure convergence to the best / most usable solutions.

The authors of [1] address the problem of automatic statistical intensity-based method for extracting 3D cerebrovascular structures from time-of-flight (TOF) magnetic resonance angiography (MRA) data. It presents a finite mixture model (FMM) to fit the intensity histogram of brain image sequences, modeling cerebral vascular structures with Gaussian distributions and other tissues with Gaussian and Rayleigh distributions. The authors propose an enhanced particle swarm optimization (PSO) algorithm for estimating FMM parameters, improving convergence by introducing a perturbation term and employing a ring-shaped neighborhood topology. The main contributions of this work are threefold. First, it underscores the importance of accurate alignment between the FMM and the intensity histogram, particularly in regions where vessels intersect with other tissues. Second, it introduces a novel FMM that combines Rayleigh and Gaussian distributions to effectively model the entire histogram, leading to more stable parameter estimation, particularly in cerebrovascular regions. Third, it presents an intelligent optimization approach, the improved PSO algorithm, for parameter estimation. This refined PSO algorithm is faster and more robust than traditional methods like Expectation Maximization (EM) and Stochastic Expectation Maximization (SEM). However, the paper acknowledges limitations in parallel processing and the consideration of voxel neighborhoods.

[2] addresses the issue of segmenting color images by simultaneously optimizing three objectives (overall deviation, edge value, and connectivity measure), using a multi-objective evolutionary algorithm (MOEA). Traditional image segmentation techniques often rely on a single composite objective function, while this approach allows for the independent consideration of each objective. By doing so, it guides the search process towards discovering a set of non-dominated and near-optimal segmentation solutions. The authors assess its effectiveness through experiments conducted on benchmark color images. To quantitatively evaluate the quality of segmentation, the paper extends the Probabilistic Rand Index (PRI) to accommodate multi-objective segmentation. The results demonstrate that the proposed method can partition color images into segments that align well with human visual perception. It automatically determines the appropriate number of segments, reducing the need for manual intervention.

A survey of the applications of evolutionary optimization applied to computer vision is provided in [3]. The paper addresses the synergy between computer vision (CV) and evolutionary computation (EC) within the domain of image analysis. Image-related tasks in CV pose considerable challenges due to factors such as image variability, high dimensionality, domain-specific expertise, and image distortions. Evolutionary computation methods have made significant strides in addressing these challenges in image analysis; however, a comprehensive survey of these approaches has been lacking. The authors make a survey that covers a wide spectrum of EC techniques applied to critical image analysis tasks. These tasks encompass fundamental areas such as edge detection, image segmentation, image feature analysis, image classification, and object detection. The survey employs a task-based taxonomy, which facilitates a deeper understanding of how EC techniques are effectively employed to tackle various image analysis challenges. Moreover, it classifies EC approaches based on representation methods, EC methods (e.g., GA, GP, PSO), optimization objectives (single-objective or multi-objective), and application domains. The paper also discusses the broader landscape of evolutionary computer vision (ECV). It explores the applications, ongoing challenges, issues, and emerging trends in this field. [4] presents the development of an innovative computer-aided design (CAD) environment centered around the concept of an evolutionary optimization algorithm. This environment enables the generation and modification of designs within predefined frameworks using problem-specific encodings and operations like recombination, crossover, and mutation. Users interact with the system through a graphical user interface to evaluate candidate designs. The authors provide several illustrative examples, including the creation of two-dimensional polygonal shapes, fractal images, path generation for mechanical planar linkages, and pattern generation for quilting. The interactive design environment was tested with various users, including children, artists, and engineers. The resulting designs were in some cases surprising, aligning with the concept of creative design. Users acknowledged the critical role of the computational environment in achieving these designs. The paper highlights several observations: consistent improvement in design quality across the user population, even with inconsistent user input; a tendency for designs to become repetitive in later stages, focusing on refinement rather than initial creativity; the complexity of the encoding required for sophisticated designs, showcasing the extensive design information processed by users; and the potential for expanding the system to support multiple evaluation

criteria, such as form, color, and layout. The paper from [5] addresses the issue of preprocessing images for computer vision, specifically, an approach that combines genetic algorithms (GAs) with Image Quality Assessment (IQA) methods to systematically enhance the quality of low-light images. The core of this approach consists of several key elements: an initial low-light image in need of improvement, a sequence of predefined image transformations (e.g., brightness adjustment, dehazing, histogram modification), and the use of an IQA method to assess image quality. The IQA score serves as a fitness measure in the GA, guiding the systematic exploration of transformation sequences to enhance image quality. The method is tested on various state-of-the-art low-light image databases, demonstrating its effectiveness in producing enhanced images. [6] introduces a method called Constrained pose Hypothesis Set Elimination (CHSEL), which addresses the challenging task of estimating plausible poses for rigid objects using volumetric information, particularly data acquired from contact events. This problem is particularly intricate as contact data inherently contains less information compared to visual data, making the pose estimation problem under-constrained when only a limited number of contact points are available. Rather than aiming to pinpoint the precise object pose, the objective of this work is to estimate a set of plausible poses that conform to the constraints imposed by the sensor data. CHSEL distinguishes itself through three fundamental attributes. First, it incorporates volumetric data, enabling the inclusion of information from both surface and free space points encountered during the robot's movement. CHSEL employs a differentiable volumetric cost function, which facilitates the efficient optimization of poses based on the available data. This differentiability allows for the application of gradient-based optimization techniques. [7] presents the application of evolutionary algorithms (EAs) to the task of automatic image enhancement, treating it as an optimization problem. Three specific EAs, namely Genetic Algorithm (GA), Differential Evolution (DE), and Self Organizing Migration Algorithm (SOMA), are employed to find an optimal set of parameters for enhancing images, with the goal of maximizing a fitness criterion related to image contrast and detail visibility. The authors make a comparative analysis of these three EAs, along with a benchmarking comparison against the histogram equalization (HE) method. The results indicate that SOMA outperforms both GA and DE in terms of image enhancement quality. It not only produces superior enhanced images with greater detail enhancement but also requires a smaller population size and exhibits lower variance between different runs of the algorithm. Additionally, SOMA results in a flatter histogram, implying a more even grayscale distribution. However, it also exhibits a higher computational time requirement and a dependency on parameter selection, necessitating extensive experimentation to determine suitable parameter values. Despite these challenges, its superior performance justifies its use for automatic image enhancement, particularly when quality is the most important factor. [8] presents a method for enhancing the contrast of medical images, aiming to improve image quality and highlight important information. The main contribution lies in the refinement of the Gamma correction method using the World Cup Optimization (WCO) algorithm. It does so by considering factors such as entropy, edge content, and multi-objective optimization. The authors compare the performance of the proposed technique with five state-of-the-art methods using various performance metrics, including contrast, homogeneity, weighted average peak signal-to-noise ratio (WPSNR), measure of enhancement (EME), and contrast-to-noise ratio (CNR). The results demonstrate that the multi-objective optimization algorithm significantly enhances image contrast and provides more

image details compared to existing methods. This enhancement is particularly valuable in the context of medical imaging, where accurate contrast enhancement plays a critical role in applications such as cancer detection. The authors of [9] present the application of the Fly Algorithm, a cooperative co-evolution algorithm applied to the optimization problem of tomography reconstruction in positron emission tomography (PET). The algorithm optimizes the positions of 3-D points to estimate the concentration of a radiotracer within the body, addressing the challenging ill-posed inverse problem of tomography. During the optimization process, various data, including image metrics, duration, and internal states, are generated and recorded in a log file. The authors propose using information visualization and user interaction techniques to explore this internal data, aiming to understand the behavior of the algorithm during the evolutionary loop. The main contributions involve demonstrating how interactive visualization techniques, such as Parallel Coordinate Plots, scatterplots, and image displays, can be employed to analyze the complex temporal data of the algorithm. These techniques allow for a better understanding of its behavior over time and facilitate the identification of points at which early termination could be triggered. The results show that a 60% reduction in the number of iterations can be achieved without sacrificing accuracy. They also highlight the potential of using interactive visualization and data exploration to enhance the performance of special-purpose evolutionary algorithms. The paper from [10] focuses on scenarios where traditional analytical objective functions for evolutionary algorithms are unavailable. In such cases, fitness evaluations rely on computationally expensive numerical simulations or historical data, making it essential to adapt optimization techniques to handle these data-driven challenges. This work addresses the concept of data-driven evolutionary optimization, which has gained increasing relevance in real-world applications. The paper presents a taxonomy of data-driven evolutionary optimization problems based on several key factors such as the nature of the available data, the feasibility of generating new data during optimization, and the strategies employed to manage surrogate models. To illustrate the practical implications of this approach, the authors consider five case studies drawn from various domains: blast furnace optimization, trauma system design, fused magnesium furnace optimization, airfoil shape design, and the design of an air intake ventilation system.

The authors of [11] propose evolutionary strategies that configure the opacity and colour transfer functions for volume visualization. Piecewise linear transfer functions are considered, with a preset number of segments. A chromosome indicates a potential function, by encoding its vertices. The objective function illustrates the variations of the images in YUV format, in 8 manually selected pixels. If these pixels are distributed over all relevant regions of the image, they could provide a conclusive and rapid assessment of the effect produced by the transfer functions. The algorithm computes the Euclidean distances between the intensities of these pixels and uses the smallest distance (to the nearest neighbour) as the objective value. The goal is to find the configuration of the transfer functions that maximize the dispersion. The study also presents a method for hierarchical clustering of light sources, which exploits a similar dispersion metric. However, in this case, the dispersion is computed for all pixels, using thumbnails of different resolutions. The clustering method considers a graph-based representation, in which the lights are associated with the nodes, and the edge costs are set inversely proportional to the dispersion. The lights producing similar lighting effects are grouped to the same cluster, by

minimizing the total cost of edges going from the nodes of a cluster to the nodes of the other clusters. The algorithm starts with random initial positions of lights, filters the lights with reduced impact, and clusters the remaining ones using the previously described strategy. [12] provides a systematic literature review of differential evolution (DE) algorithm variants, focusing of applications for image processing. The authors discuss multiple aspects of DE: basic DE, its advantages and disadvantages, and proposed mutation strategies; modified DE variants offered using a new parameter selection policy, mutation strategy, and hybridized with other algorithms; variants of DE which solve specific problems in image processing. The study concludes that the implementation of DE in the multi-objective domain is limited, and there is a scope for future research in this direction. [13] proposes a co-evolutionary algorithm for the construction of digital mosaic images. Every individual corresponds to a tile that should be placed in the image and the image is formed using the whole population. In this context, the global objective function illustrates the overall performance of the population, being defined as the total absolute error between the resulting mosaic image and reference image. The local objective function assesses the quality of a tile by showing its impact on the global performance, i.e., it results as the total absolute error obtained without the tile. The values of local and global objective functions are computed for a predefined reference, which means that the algorithm should be executed for each image exemplification. A tile is represented by position, rotation angle, scaling factors, and colour. However, in the context of our approach, using non-reference quality metrics is compulsory. [14] presents a new feature selection technique for image classification. The proposed method is based on the integration of genetic algorithm (GA) and particle swarm optimization (PSO). The main objective of this technique is to select the most informative features in terms of classification accuracies. The proposed method is tested on two different scenarios. In the first scenario, the feature selection approach is performed on a well-known hyperspectral data set, i.e., the AVIRIS Indian Pines. Results demonstrate that the method can significantly increase the classification accuracy of the raw data in an acceptable CPU processing time. In the second scenario, the proposed feature selection technique is applied on a set of features derived by attribute profiles, to select the most discriminative features for detecting roads from a background. Results infer that the method is able to detect roads in a complex urban image with acceptable accuracy. The proposed method can find informative bands in terms of classification accuracies in an acceptable CPU time, and can therefore be used for road detection. In the novel feature selection approach, there is no need to set the number of output features since the proposed approach can automatically select the most useful features in terms of classification accuracies. The authors of [15] propose a multi-agent-based methods of generating 3D city landscapes. The layout is encoded using several arrays that describe the land/water configuration, the street map, the heights and locations of buildings, etc. The evolutionary algorithm is interactive and allows the user to select some preferred configurations. These configurations are exploited by a separate agent who is responsible for adapting the selection for recombination based on user preferences. [16] The paper presents a multi-population cooperative evolution-based image segmentation algorithm to solve the accurate segmentation problem of complex helical surface image. The paper presents a multi-direction evolutionary based image segmentation model for complex helical surface image. The segmentation model extracts different image eigenvectors that can represent the critical characteristics of complex helical surface image, and then, the segmentation problem of helical

surface image can be transformed into a problem of multiple eigenvectors segmentation. The grey distribution of pixels in complex helical surface image does not have a certain regular pattern, so the paper researches the method of searching threshold solutions for image segmentation from multiple feature directions at the same time, and constructs the multi-directional co-evolution. The proposed algorithm is applied to the classical test function sequence to verify the advantages and disadvantages of the proposed algorithm. The paper concludes that the proposed algorithm has application significance for the image measurement and detection of complex helical surface by computer vision method. The paper from [17] This paper investigates the performance of the MAP-elite algorithm for different encodings, in the context of an architectural design problem. The encodings considered for the comparative analysis are as follows: Direct encoding – the grid-wise layout is encoded by a matrix, each cell/element indicating the height of the building corresponding to that location; Parametric encoding – the chromosome encodes a fixed number of rectangles, which specify the locations of the buildings and their ground print, and also the corresponding heights; Dictionary-based encoding – the chromosome uses a preset number of building blocks defined by the dictionary; the dictionary has a finite size; Compositional patterns producing networks – the chromosome encodes the weights of a neural network of preset architecture and the type of the activation functions. The neural network admits as inputs the coordinates of a cell and provides the layout of buildings in an area depicted around the cell; Cellular automata – the chromosome encodes the weights that are used by the development process to build the layout. The best results were obtained for the compositional patterns producing networks, followed by dictionary-based encoding and direct encoding. The low-dimensional encoding tends to offer better diversity and fitness. Another worthy contribution for design problems is [18], which focuses on evaluating a scenario-based multiobjective evolutionary algorithm for real-world design problems. It investigates the performance of scenario-based optimization of real-world design problems using an evaluation suite that is stochastically sampled during each EA generation. Using a scenario-based scheme to address uncertainty in a real-world system's operational environment, system designs are developed via aggregating the performance of a solution evaluated across many scenarios. Within each generation of the evolutionary algorithm the evaluation suite is resampled and evaluated by the current generation's solutions.

The paper [19] describes a rule-enhanced transfer function generation method for medical volume visualization. The rules are defined based on the local frequency distribution of a voxel's neighborhood, as local frequency distribution has been shown to offer a novel and effective manner for feature identification. A Genetic Algorithm is employed to select the set of rules that are most effective in distinguishing the target tissue from other tissues, and connected component analysis is used to refine the rule-evaluation results. Another contribution in medical imaging is [20], which presents a version of the Fly Algorithm dedicated to tomographic reconstruction, where the flies are mimicking radioactive photon sources. In classical EAs at the end of the algorithm the best individual is extracted and considered the solution of the optimisation problem, while all the rest of the population is discarded. The Fly Algorithm, which is a Cooperative Co-evolution algorithm relies on a different philosophy, where each individual is a part of the solution. An individual corresponds to a 3-D point. The whole population is a representation of the reconstructed tomographic images. The evaluation of the performance of

each individual is performed using a fitness function based on the leave-one-out-cross-validation method. In the nuclear medicine context, the concentration of flies will be an estimation of the radioactive concentration. Evolution is controlled using a fitness function based on the discrepancy of the projections simulated by the flies with the actual pattern received by the sensors. The reconstructed radioactive concentration is derived from the population of flies, i.e. a collection of points in the 3-D Euclidean space, after convergence. In the field of volume visualization, the authors of [21] make use of qualitative images (may be real world images or any other images already classified as qualitative by some clearly defined metrics) and evolutionary algorithms to generate transfer functions so that the end-result is very similar to the selected images. The method uses deep neural networks (to assess transfer function cost as a scalar difference between rendered image and selected image) and evolutionary algorithms. 1D transfer functions are considered (x-axis is the data value, y-axis is the opacity value). To control the size of the transfer function search space and increase search speed, the x and y axis were coarsened: x-axis (256 discrete values) was divided into 8 ranges of 32 points each; y-axis (256 discrete values) was divided into 8 points. The ranges and points were allowed to slide/shift values over the initial non-coarsened domains in the newly generated chromosomes (transfer functions).

4 Quality-Diversity Methods

QD optimization algorithms aim to find sets of optimal solutions which result from local optimization within regions resulting from a partitioning of the corresponding search space. Unlike most conventional optimization methods, QD methods do not operate directly in the solution space, but rather define a different search space (the feature space) in which the optimization is carried out. Also unlike other categories of optimizers, QD methods first partition the feature space into regions where optimization is carried out locally. Consequently, such methods do not produce globally-optimal solutions, but rather a set of locally optimal ones, spread across the feature space. The output of such methods is a set of locally-best solutions which constitute a characterization of the entire search space. The commonly-use term in the related field is “illumination”, i.e. QD methods “illuminate” the feature space by finding sets of solutions that constitute a representation or a mapping of the quality of the solutions within the entire feature domain. Therefore, such methods offer a built-in mechanism for ensuring diversity in the resulting solution population. Rather than presenting the global-best solution, such methods offer multiple and diverse locally-best solutions. For this reason, we find that such methods are good candidates for fulfilling our objectives. An introduction into QD algorithms is provided in [22], where the general principle of such methods is detailed: instead of searching for the optimum of the cost function, they provide a large set of high-performing solutions (typically a few thousands) that differ according to a few user-defined features of interest. One can use the resulting set to better understand how features of solutions influence performance. The most commonly used categories of QD methods are variations of the MAP-Elites algorithm [23]. Many authors make use of such approaches in various fields and, though there is a predominance of MAP-Elites applications in robotics and guidance systems, many relevant works are tangential to our areas of interest. A contribution which facilitates the implementation of such methods is presented in [24], which describes a library built on a highly modular

conceptual QD framework. By replacing components in the conceptual framework users can compose algorithms from across the QD literature. The RIBS framework that consists of three core components: (1) an archive storing solutions generated by the QD algorithm, (2) emitters generating solutions for evaluation, and (3) a scheduler managing the interaction of the archive and emitters and providing the primary ask-tell interface to the user.

Since the onset of the original paper, many variations of MAP-Elites and their applications have been proposed. In this context, the authors of [25] discuss various algorithms, such as Novelty Search with Local Competition (NSLC), Multi-dimensional Archive of Phenotypic Elites (MAP-Elites), and Centroidal Voronoi Tessellation (CVT) MAP-Elites. These algorithms require users to specify bounds, but the authors introduce variants that automatically expand their bounds based on discovered solutions. It introduces a new algorithm called “Cluster-Elites”, capable of adapting its bounds to non-convex spaces. The study compares these algorithms in a maze navigation problem and finds that Cluster-Elites and the expanded versions of MAP-Elites and CVT-MAP-Elites perform as well as, or better than, NSLC, MAP-Elites, and CVT-MAP-Elites. This raises two key questions: whether expansive versions of these algorithms can be as effective as their fixed-bounds counterparts and whether an algorithm that allocates centroids based on actual behavior space shape, like Cluster-Elites, is more effective. The results suggest that expansive variants of MAP-Elites and CVT-MAP-Elites perform comparably to fixed-bounds versions and NSLC without needing prior knowledge of bounds. Cluster-Elites also shows promise, especially in complex tasks with non-convex behavior space shapes. Combining NSLC with Cluster-Elites may offer advantages over both algorithms.

The paper from [26] provides a comprehensive review of solution set quality evaluation. Starting with the basic principles and concepts of set quality evaluation, it summarises and categorises 100 state-of-the-art quality indicators, with the focus on what quality aspects these indicators reflect. A straightforward way to compare the quality of solution sets is visualisation. However, visual comparison fails to quantify the difference between solution sets and also becomes harder with more objectives involved. Quality indicators (QIs) overcome the issues of visual comparison by mapping a solution set into a real number, thereby providing quantitative differences between solution sets. QIs are capable of delivering precise statements of solution set quality, for example, in which quality aspect one set is better than another and how much better is one set than another in certain aspects. The final conclusion is that there is no ideal quality indicator to evaluate solution sets and different indicators are more fit than others in different situations. The authors of [27] introduce a simple extension to MAP-Elites that has a constant, pre-defined number of regions irrespective of the dimensionality of the feature space. The main insight is that methods from computational geometry could partition a high-dimensional space into well-spread geometric regions. In particular, the algorithm uses a Centroidal Voronoi Tessellation (CVT) to divide the feature space into a desired number of regions; it then places every generated individual in its closest region, replacing a less fit one if the region is already occupied. [28] presents Multi-Emitter MAP-Elites (ME-MAP-Elites), a direct extension of Covariance Matrix Adaptation MAP-Elites (CMA-ME) [29], in which instead of using exclusively one type of emitter, multiple emitter types are used together in a heterogeneous emitter set. Moreover, the proportion of each emitter type used at each generation is dynamically adjusted by using a bandit algorithm to automatically find the most appropriate

distribution of emitter types depending on the situation. The paper from [30] presents a QD-based solution to solving multiple tasks at once. To this extent, the authors propose a fitness function that is parameterized by a task descriptor and returns the fitness value. They also introduce Multi-task MAP-Elites which divides the feature space into niches and holds the highest-performing individual found so far for each niche. The authors hypothesize that high-performing solutions that QD algorithms find are different but similar in the genotypic space. They also compare their approach to reinforcement learning for multi-task learning and report that their algorithm is more capable for multi-task problems. A similar problem is handled by [31], which proposes an extension of the MAP-Elites algorithm in the multi-objective setting: Multi-Objective MAP-Elites (MOME). Namely, it combines the diversity inherited from the MAP-Elites grid algorithm with the strength of multi-objective optimizations by filling each cell with a Pareto Front. The idea behind MOME is to progressively cover the descriptor space while building Elite Pareto fronts, i.e. Pareto fronts that maximize the hyper-volume in each niche. In opposition to MAP-Elites that maintains either none or a single solution in each cell, MOME stores Pareto fronts of solutions in each cell. [32] attempts to assess the reliability of Quality Diversity (QD) algorithms, particularly grid-based QD algorithms. The benchmark involves optimizing the Rastrigin function, a well-known artificial function used to evaluate global optimization methods. Unlike traditional global optimization benchmarks, the focus here is on exhaustively exploring the landscape rather than just finding the global minimum. The study specifically compares the reliability of two versions of the MAP-Elites algorithm on the Rastrigin function, providing a methodology to evaluate the performance of QD algorithms in exploring complex landscapes.

The paper from [33] introduces an interactive evolutionary algorithm based on Quality Diversity (QD) search, aiming to provide user-driven control while minimizing user fatigue. The algorithm, called User Controlled MAP-Elites (UC-ME), employs a window-based approach within the behavioral space to focus on specific regions guided by the user's selections. It adapts to both unconstrained and constrained problems through dual archives of feasible and infeasible elites. UC-ME is tested in the context of generating architectural layouts, a complex and constrained design problem, using artificial users with different selection criteria. The results demonstrate that UC-ME effectively caters to various user goals, focusing on interesting parts of the problem space according to the user's preferences. However, it achieves this at the expense of lower coverage and fewer elites compared to traditional QD algorithms. In [34], the authors introduce the Surrogate-Assisted Illumination (SAIL), an algorithm designed to enhance the efficiency of quality-diversity algorithms, such as MAP-Elites, in the context of design optimization. The core motivation for SAIL arises from the need to overcome the computational limitations of illumination techniques when exploring vast design spaces. Unlike traditional optimization methods that focus on finding a single optimal solution, illumination algorithms seek to provide a diverse set of high-quality solutions in a single run. SAIL achieves this goal by integrating surrogate modeling techniques, and thus reducing the number of fitness evaluations required. It operates by first constructing a surrogate model based on initial solutions. Then, it employs MAP-Elites to generate solutions that maximize the acquisition function within various regions of the feature space. This process generates an acquisition map, from which new samples are drawn and evaluated. The collected observations further refine the surrogate model, resulting

in increasingly accurate representations of high-fitness regions within the feature space. SAIL efficiently explores design spaces, producing diverse, high-performing designs even when computational resources are limited. Its versatility allows it to be applied across different domains, including complex tasks such as aerodynamic simulations. The same method is addressed in [35], where the effectiveness of SAIL is demonstrated in a 2D airfoil design problem, where it outperforms MAP-Elites by requiring far fewer evaluations to find high-quality solutions. SAIL operates by creating surrogate models based on initial solutions, employing MAP-Elites to maximize acquisition functions, and iteratively refining these models to predict optimal designs. This allows for rapid exploration and visualization of design spaces, even when precise evaluations are limited.

Multiple other efforts have invested in improving MAP-Elites and its variations, some proposing interesting, original ideas. In [36], the authors presents Deep-Grid MAP-Elites, where all individuals encountered during the optimisation process are added to the container in the cell they belong to. As long as this cell is not full, they are simply added to it without discarding any existing solutions. However, as soon as the cell is full, the new solutions replace individuals randomly chosen among the ones already in the cell. The respective fitness of the individuals and the time-of-appearance are not taken into account to remove any potential bias. [37] introduces the concept of computer-aided ideation: the usage of QD in conjunction with dimensionality reduction and standard clustering techniques, grouping similar solutions into classes and their representative prototypes. The prototypes resulted from QD can be selected to constrain QD in a next iteration of design space exploration by seeding it with the selected prototype class (this is a recursive process). The similarity space can be used continuously as it is decoupled from the feature map. This allows the diversity metric, the feature characterization, to change between iterations. The order in which the feature dimensions are chosen can be customized depending on the design process. For example, the engineer can start searching the design space in terms of diversity of design and later on switch to functional features. [38] introduces Differential MAP-Elites, which combines elements of Differential Evolution with CVT-MAP-Elites. The algorithm is designed to solve multimodal optimization problems and generate diverse solutions. The paper discusses the challenges of finding a suitable sigma parameter and the limitations of mutations based on short-tailed distributions. The authors compare their algorithm with CVT-MAP-Elites and show that Differential MAP-Elites finds more accurate and diverse solutions. An original idea is presented in [39], where the authors suggest that there is an inherent limitation of the objective-based paradigm in evolutionary algorithms and other approaches to guide the search might provide better results. The paper proposes a means of circumventing deception that yields a new perspective on open-ended evolution: instead of either explicitly seeking an objective or modeling natural evolution to capture open-endedness, the idea is to simply search for behavioral novelty. Even in an objective-based problem, such novelty search ignores the objective.

The paper from [40] investigates the output diversity of QD search working in parametric space vs. in the corresponding latent space produced by a variational autoencoder. The experiments are done for a shape-generation problem, using a single objective function that relies on the symmetry of the artefacts. The diversity of a set relies on the distance to the closest neighbour computed for its elements. The search is carried out by the Voronoi-Elites algorithm, which keeps the size of the archive constant but defines an increasing number of niches using the Voronoi tessellation. When the maximum number of niches is reached, the archive evolves by

forming pairs of similar solutions and eliminating the worst artefact from each. This strategy permits preserving enough diverse elites in the first generation when the population is distributed over the whole search space. The results show that diversity is better for the QD algorithm working in the parametric search space. [41] introduces a method for the design of a hierarchical surrogate illumination model. The surrogate model provides a fast estimation of the objective function, to compare the solutions during the evolutionary process. In line with the grid of niches adopted by the Map-Elite algorithm, the surrogate model is defined as an ensemble of heterogeneous components, where each component is specialised to a bin depicted in the feature space, and it is assigned with a confidence level. Simple models could be thus aggregated, to decrease the prediction variance and avoid overfitting. This advantageously exploits the blessing of uncertainty, to generate smoother approximations of the objective function. [42] proposes an extension of MAP-Elites using a custom emitter which uses differentiable functions to optimize the search over discrete feature spaces. The gradient information of the objective is exploited by mutation, to produce new solutions that are inserted into the repertoire. The gradient is computed for a linear aggregation of the objective function and quality-diversity descriptors, assuming that a definition in a continuous space is available for these functions. In this aggregation, the weights are set randomly, and the gradients are normalised. The mutants result by flipping a single position, randomly chosen. The positions that produce large variations of the aggregated function are assigned with the big selection probabilities. The probabilities are controlled by a temperature parameter which is adjusted to ensure that the flip distribution reaches, on average, a target Shannon entropy. A mutant is accepted into a cell, only if it has a better fitness than the existing solution. This hybridisation between quality diversity and gradient methods can improve both the convergence speed and the accuracy of the algorithm. In [43], the evolutionary algorithm configures a 2D layout based on a reference, starting from a white canvas. The cells coloured during the evolutionary loop are depicted with different shapes and locations. A cell is associated with a chromosome which encodes the location of the central pixel and necessary details about the cell's geometry and colour. Every generation, a fixed number of elites deterministically depicted from the population participate in image reconstruction. The objective function is defined as the absolute error between the current image and the reference; for supplementary protection, a colourization scheme proposed for a cell is accepted only if the objective value is smaller than a threshold. This difference is computed in a feature space defined by means of an edge mask, R channel map, and grayscale image. The paper from [44] presents an algorithm called IC-MAP-Elites, which is used for mixed-initiative procedural content generation. The algorithm is designed to explore the expressive range of all possible dimension combinations in several scenarios and to evaluate their influence on the fitness landscape and overall performance of the content generation process. The paper also discusses the importance of using comparison metrics that can measure emergent properties of the generated content and identifies bias in the search space. The authors conducted a second set of experiments analyzing the expressive range of the IC-MAP-Elites using the 21 possible combinations of dimension pairs. The results indicate that there are specific dimensions in level generation that foster greater exploration not only in their respective dimensions but also in all the others due to the diverse individuals generated within the respective dimensions. The paper concludes by suggesting that the IC-MAP-Elites algorithm can be used to guide the evolutionary process in an intuitive way and incorporate suggestions produced by the algorithm in room designs. [45] proposes a QD framework for generating content according to user preferences. The user interacts with the quality diversity algorithm to indicate the preferred solutions. These preferences are mapped to an ad-hoc matrix that shows

the positions of selections. User preferences are integrated into the evolutionary process by updating the fitness values. The updates are controlled by a neural model that is trained after each interaction with the user. Training is performed for a data set generated from feasible populations with adjustments suggested by the ad-hoc matrix. [46] introduces a customisation of the MAP -Elites algorithm to tackle constrained optimisations for which small violations of the constraints are allowed. Each constraint is mapped to a distinct feature, so the feature vector illustrates all constraint violations. The discretisation of the feature space is done according to the tolerance levels defined for each constraint. Experimental analysis shows that the MAP -Elites algorithm is not effective for problems with small feasible regions or non-separable equality constraints, because much exploration effort is spent on finding feasible solutions, at the expense of optimisation. The issue of user-interactive optimization is handled by [47], where in the evolutionary loop of the QD method the user can indicate the preference for some solutions. Based on this selection, a user selection drift distance is computed for each available solution; this metric relies on the distance to the closest selected and unselected elites, and it is computed in a space of reduced dimension resulting from the genotypic space via t-distributed stochastic neighbour embedding. This dimension reduction allows a more relevant similarity analysis. The user selection drift is afterward used for penalising the fitness values, to promote solutions aligned with user preferences. Experimental investigations done for a multimodal trajectory planning problem illustrate smaller user selection drifts than in the case when selected solutions are injected by seeding. This permits the preservation of a diverse archive.

The paper from [48] describes a framework for QD algorithms and abstracts notions like archive/collection, solution selection operators and solution characterisation values (fitness, novelty scores etc). The objective of a QD-algorithm is to generate a collection of both diverse and high-performing solutions. This collection represents a (model free) projection of the highdimensional search space into a lower dimensional space defined by the solution descriptors. The quality of a collection is defined by its coverage of the descriptor space and by the global quality of the solutions that are kept in the collection. The paper introduces a new score, named the Curiosity Score, that can be used to bias the selection. The curiosity score represents the propensity of an individual to generate offspring that are added to the collection. A practical implementation consists of increasing the curiosity score of an individual each time one of its offspring is added to the collection. Conversely, when an offspring fails to be added to the archive (because it is not novel or high-performing enough), the Curiosity Score is decreased.

5 Summary of Presented Work

We summarize the work described in previous sections in Table 1, which provides an overview of the main results discussed so far. Our main criterion for classifying the analysed results is the type of optimization being carried out. For our purposes, we mainly differentiate between conventional optimizers and QD methods, the two classes of optimizers which we experimented with thus far.

Table 1. Overview of the contributions from the related literature discussed in the report

Paper/reference	Optimization method	Main field of application	Main idea
A novel statistical cerebrovascular segmentation algorithm with particle swarm optimization [1]	Single-objective (particle swarm optimization)	Exploration of medical images	A method for extracting cerebrovascular structures from medical images using a statistical approach. It introduces an improved algorithm, combining a novel finite mixture model and particle swarm optimization for parameter estimation.
A Multi-objective Evolutionary Algorithm for Color Image Segmentation [2]	Multi-objective (Strength Pareto Evolutionary Algorithm-2, SPEA-2)	Image segmentation	A multi-objective evolutionary algorithm for segmenting color images. It simultaneously optimizes three objectives, i.e., overall deviation, edge value, and connectivity measure, resulting in segments that match human visual perception.
A Survey on Evolutionary Computation for Computer Vision and Image Analysis - Past, Present, and Future Trends [3]	Multiple (survey)	Computer vision	A survey of evolutionary computation techniques applied to computer vision tasks, addressing challenges in image analysis. It classifies such approaches by task, representation, optimization method, and domain, offering insights into their applications and limitations while guiding future research in evolutionary computer vision.
An Interactive Evolutionary Environment for Creative Design [4]	Single-objective (genetic algorithms)	3D model and 2D image design	An interactive computer-aided design environment using an evolutionary algorithm, where users, including artists and engineers, create and modify designs within predefined frameworks, yielding creative results.
Applying Genetic Algorithm and Image Quality Assessment for Reproducible Processing of Low-light Images [5]	Single-objective (genetic algorithms)	Image enhancement	An approach that combines genetic algorithms and Image Quality Assessment methods to systematically enhance the quality of low-light images.
CHSEL Producing Diverse Plausible Pose Estimates from Contact and Free Space Data [6]	Quality-diversity (CHSEL-original)	Pose estimation in volume data	Constrained pose Hypothesis Set Elimination (CHSEL), a method for estimating plausible object poses from limited contact data. CHSEL uses volumetric information, a differentiable cost function, and Quality Diversity optimization to generate a diverse set of high-quality poses, addressing the challenge of under-constrained pose estimation.
Comparative analysis of evolutionary algorithms for image enhancement [7]	Single-objective (GA, DE, SOMA-original)	Image enhancement	The application of evolutionary algorithms to optimize automatic image enhancement. The study aims to maximize image contrast and detail visibility. Among the algorithms, Self Organizing Migration Algorithm (SOMA) stands out as the most effective, producing superior enhanced images with minimal population size and variance. However, parameter selection remains crucial for its performance.
Contrast enhancement of medical images using a new version of the	Multi-objective (World Cup)	Medical image enhancement	A method for enhancing the contrast of medical images using a modified Gamma correction technique based on the World Cup Optimization (WCO) algorithm. By optimizing the selection of the Gamma value through entropy, edge content,

Paper/reference	Optimization method	Main field of application	Main idea
World Cup Optimization algorithm [8]	Optimization, WCO)		and multi-objective optimization, the method improves image quality and information clarity, making it valuable for medical imaging applications.
Data exploration in evolutionary reconstruction of PET images [9]	Parisian Evolution (Fly Algorithm)	Medical image enhancement	The Fly Algorithm is used for tomography reconstruction in positron emission tomography and interactive visualization is employed to understand the behavior of the algorithm.
Data-Driven Evolutionary Optimization - An Overview and Case Studies [10]	Data-driven optimization: multi-objective (4 problems), single-objective (1 problem)	Multiple design-related problems	Addresses data-driven evolutionary optimization, focusing on scenarios where traditional objective functions are unavailable, necessitating costly simulations or historical data for fitness evaluation. It classifies these challenges and presents real-world case studies.
Design Galleries - A General Approach to Setting Parameters for Computer Graphics and Animation [11]	Single objective, evolutionary strategies, configuration of the transfer functions, dispersion	Volume visualization	A method for determining pieewise linear transfer functions and light source clustering for volume visualization by exploiting the distributions of pixel neighborhoods.
Differential Evolution and Its Applications in Image Processing Problems - A Comprehensive Review [12]	Survey, multi-objective, differential evolution	Image processing	A systematic literature review of differential evolution (DE) algorithm variants, focusing of applications for image processing.
Fly4Arts: Evolutionary Digital Art with the Fly Algorithm [13]	Single objective, evolutionary strategy	Digital art	Co-evolutionary algorithm for digital mosaic construction with global and local objective functions.
Feature selection based on hybridization of genetic algorithm and particle swarm optimization [14]	Embedded feature selection, GA + PSO	Image understanding	Novel feature selection technique combines genetic algorithm and particle swarm optimization to enhance image classification accuracy. Tested successfully on hyperspectral data and road detection, it automatically selects informative features, eliminating the need to set the number of output features.
Multi-agent evolutionary systems for the generation of complex virtual worlds [15]	Interactive evolutionary algorithms, agents	3D model design	A 3D cityscape generation system employing a multi-agent approach. Various arrays encode city layout details like land/water, street maps, building heights, and locations. The interactive evolutionary algorithm enables user selection of preferred configurations, which are then used by a dedicated agent to guide recombination based on user preferences.
Multi-population cooperative evolution-based image segmentation algorithm for complex helical surface image [16]	Multi-objective optimization, PSO	Image segmentation	A multi-population cooperative evolution-based algorithm for accurately segmenting complex helical surface images. The algorithm extracts various image eigenvectors representing critical characteristics of these images, transforming the segmentation problem into a multi-eigenvector segmentation task.
On the Suitability of Representations for Quality Diversity Optimization of Shapes [17]	Quality-diversity, shape problem, encoding	3D voxel-based design	Evaluation of the performance of the MAP-Elite algorithm using various encodings in the context of architectural design. The encodings include direct, parametric, dictionary-based, compositional patterns producing networks, and cellular automata.
Stochastic Scenario Evaluation in Evolutionary Algorithms Used for	Multi-objective, genetic programming	Design optimization	A multiobjective evolutionary algorithm for real-world design problems that relies on scenarios. It assesses how well this

Paper/reference	Optimization method	Main field of application	Main idea
Robust Scenario-Based Optimization [18]			algorithm optimizes real-world designs by sampling evaluations during each generation of the algorithm.
Rule-Enhanced Transfer Function Generation for Medical Volume Visualization [19]	Single-objective (genetic algorithms)	Volume visualization	A method for generating transfer functions in medical volume visualization. It utilizes rules based on the local frequency distribution of voxel neighborhoods to identify features effectively. A Genetic Algorithm is employed to select the best rules for distinguishing the target tissue from others, and connected component analysis further refines the rule-based evaluation results.
Voxelisation in the 3-D Fly Algorithm for PET [20]	Parisian Evolution (Fly Algorithm)	Medical image enhancement	A version of the Fly Algorithm dedicated to tomographic reconstruction in medical imaging, where the flies are mimicking radioactive photon sources.
Photo-Guided Exploration of Volume Data Features [21]	Single-objective (genetic algorithm)	Volume visualization	Semi-automatic automatic generation of transfer functions based on comparing rendered images against reference quality ones.
Quality-Diversity Optimization: a novel branch of stochastic optimization [22]	Quality-diversity	General-purpose optimization	An introduction to Quality-Diversity optimization and the main representative algorithms.
Illuminating search spaces by mapping elites [23]	MAP-Elites	General-purpose optimization	Introduction of the MAP-Elites approach.
pyribs - A Bare-Bones Python Library for Quality Diversity Optimization [24]	Quality-diversity	General-purpose optimization	Presentation of the pyribs framework, a Python library for composing and exploiting QD algorithms.
A comparison of illumination algorithms in unbounded spaces [25]	MAP-Elites	General-purpose optimization	Comparison of QD evolutionary algorithms, including Cluster-Elites and expanded versions of MAP-Elites and CVT-MAP-Elites, which adapt their bounds without prior knowledge.
Quality Evaluation of Solution Sets in Multiobjective Optimisation - A survey [26]	Multi-objective	General-purpose optimization	Review of solution set quality evaluation methods, categorizing 100 state-of-the-art quality indicators (QIs) that provide quantitative differences between solution sets, making them more precise than visual comparison.
Using Centroidal Voronoi Tessellations to Scale Up the Multi-dimensional Archive of Phenotypic Elites Algorithm [27]	Centroidal Voronoi Tessellation MAP-Elites	General-purpose optimization	Addresses the MAP-Elites algorithm's main drawback, that it cannot scale to high-dimensional feature spaces since the number of regions increase exponentially with the number of dimensions.
Multi-Emitter MAP-Elites: Improving quality, diversity and convergence speed with heterogeneous sets of emitters [28]	Multi-Emitter MAP-Elites	General-purpose optimization	Multi-Emitter MAP-Elites (ME-MAP-Elites) is an algorithm that directly extends CMA-ME and improves its quality, diversity and data efficiency. It leverages the diversity of a heterogeneous set of emitters, in which each emitter type improves the optimisation process in different ways.
Covariance matrix adaptation for the rapid illumination of behavior space [29]	Covariance Matrix Adaptation MAP-Elites	General purpose optimization	Introduction of the use of Covariance Matrix Adaptation within MAP-Elites
Quality Diversity for Multi-task Optimization [30]	Quality-diversity, multi-task	General-purpose optimization	An extension of the MAP-Elites algorithm, called Multi-task MAPElites, that solves multiple tasks when the fitness function depends on the task.

Paper/reference	Optimization method	Main field of application	Main idea
Multi-Objective Quality Diversity Optimization [31]	Quality-diversity, multi-objective	General-purpose optimization	An extension of the MAP-Elites algorithm in the multi-objective setting, which combines the diversity inherited from the MAP-Elites grid algorithm with the strength of multi-objective optimizations by filling each cell with a Pareto Front.
Comparing reliability of grid-based Quality-Diversity algorithms using artificial landscapes [32]	Quality-diversity (MAP-Elites)	Comparison of QD methods	A benchmark for evaluating the reliability of Quality-Diversity (QD) algorithms, particularly grid-based ones, by optimizing the Rastrigin function.
Controllable Exploration of a Design Space via Interactive Quality Diversity [33]	quality-diversity (MAP-Elites)	Exploration of user behavioral space	An interactive evolutionary algorithm called User Controlled MAP-Elites (UC-ME), based on Quality Diversity (QD) search. UC-ME allows users to guide the exploration within a specific region of the behavioral space, minimizing cognitive load and user fatigue.
Data-Efficient Design Exploration through Surrogate-Assisted Illumination [34]	quality-diversity (SAIL-original, increases efficiency of MAP-Elites)	Design optimization	The Surrogate-Assisted Illumination (SAIL), an algorithm that enhances the efficiency of MAP-Elites in design optimization. SAIL integrates surrogate modeling to minimize fitness evaluations, providing diverse high-quality solutions in complex design spaces while being computationally efficient.
Data-efficient exploration, optimization, and modeling of diverse designs through surrogate-assisted illumination [35]	quality-diversity (SAIL-original, increases efficiency of MAP-Elites)	Design optimization	Application of Surrogate-Assisted Illumination (SAIL) to efficiently-explore and visualize design spaces.
Fast and stable MAP-Elites in noisy domains using deep grids [36]	Quality-diversity using deep grids	General-purpose optimization	Deep-Grid MAP-Elites is a QD method which uses an archive of previously encountered solutions to approximate the performance of a current solution.
Prototype discovery using quality-diversity [37]	Quality-diversity, dimensionality reduction, clustering	Design optimization	Combination of Quality Diversity with dimensionality reduction and clustering to group similar solutions and create representative prototypes. These prototypes guide subsequent design space exploration through a recursive process.
Self-Referential Quality Diversity Through Differential MAP-Elites [38]	Quality-diversity, differential evolution	General-purpose optimization	Differential MAP-Elites combines elements of Differential Evolution with CVT-MAP-Elites. The algorithm is designed to solve multimodal optimization problems and generate diverse solutions.
Abandoning Objectives: Evolution through the Search for Novelty Alone [39]	Alternative to objective-based optimization	General-purpose optimization	A different perspective on open-ended evolution, advocating for a focus on searching for behavioral novelty rather than solely pursuing specific objectives. This novelty-based approach can be applied even in objective-driven problems, where the objective is intentionally ignored.
Expressivity of Parameterized and Data-driven Representations in Quality Diversity Search [40]	Single objective, quality diversity, shape-generation problem	Shape generation	Use of Quality Diversity analysis in the context of a shape-generation problem, comparing the output diversity of Voronoi-Elites search in parametric space and latent space produced by a variational autoencoder.
Hierarchical Surrogate Modeling for Illumination Algorithms [41]	Surrogate model as alternative to MAP-Elites	General-purpose optimization	A hierarchical surrogate illumination model for efficient objective function estimation in quality-diversity evolutionary processes. It uses an ensemble of specialized components based on a niche grid, allowing aggregation of simple models to reduce prediction variance and enhance accuracy.

Paper/reference	Optimization method	Main field of application	Main idea
Gradient-Informed Quality Diversity for the Illumination of Discrete Spaces [42]	Quality diversity, mutation based on gradient of objective	General-purpose optimization	An extension of MAP-Elites using differentiable functions in a custom emitter for optimizing discrete feature spaces. It leverages gradient information for mutation, creating new solutions in the repertoire.
Image-Guided Rendering with an Evolutionary Algorithm Based on Cloud Model [43]	Cooperative evolutionary algorithms, 2D image, with a Reference image	Image generation	An evolutionary algorithm that designs a 2D layout relative to a reference image, starting with a blank canvas. Cells on the canvas are represented by chromosomes encoding their position, geometry, and color. During each generation, a fixed number of elite cells contribute to image creation. The objective is to minimize the absolute error between the evolving image and the reference.
Interactive Constrained MAP-Elites Analysis and Evaluation of the Expressiveness of the Feature Dimensions [44]	MAP-Elites with constraints	Design optimization	Introduction of IC-MAP-Elites, an algorithm for mixed-initiative procedural content generation. It explores various dimension combinations in scenarios to assess their impact on content generation performance, emphasizing the importance of comparison metrics for emergent properties.
Learning the Designer's Preferences to Drive Evolution [45]	Quality diversity, interactive aggregation of preferences and search	User-driven design	a quality diversity framework for content generation based on user preferences. Users interact with the algorithm to select preferred solutions, which are mapped onto a matrix. These preferences influence the evolutionary process by updating fitness values using a neural model.
MAP-Elites for Constrained Optimization [46]	MAP-Elites with constraints	General-purpose optimization	A customized version of the MAP-Elites algorithm designed for constrained optimizations with small allowable constraint violations. Each constraint is represented as a distinct feature in the feature vector, and discretization of the feature space is based on defined tolerance levels for each constraint.
Modeling user selection in quality diversity [47]	Quality diversity, interactive aggregation of preferences and search	User-driven design	An interactive quality diversity algorithm where users can indicate preferences for solutions during the evolutionary process. The algorithm computes a user selection drift distance for each solution, considering proximity to both selected and unselected elites in a reduced-dimensional space.
Quality and diversity optimization - A unifying modular framework [48]	Quality-diversity	General-purpose optimization	Introduction of the "Curiosity Score" as a new metric to influence selection, which measures an individual's tendency to produce offspring added to the collection. In practice, an individual's Curiosity Score increases when its offspring are included and decreases when offspring fail to meet inclusion criteria.

6 Conclusions

The related literature discussed in this report offered valuable insight into the applications of evolutionary optimization in fields related to VolEvol. While this report is by no means an exhaustive analysis of all relevant related work, most analysed results have proven promising from multiple perspectives: firstly, conducting this survey improved our understanding of how such methods are applied for solving various problems related to image processing, image understanding and visualization; secondly, many of the consulted papers offered useful ideas and opportunities for improvement with regard to the methods developed within VolEvol. In particular, QD methods seem to be promising candidates for use as evolutionary optimization tools, in no small part due to their inbuilt mechanism for introducing diversity into the resulting image population. However, we do not discount other non-QD approaches, as they offer their own advantages. One important aspect in this regard is that methods relying on global single- and multi-optimization strategies require a separate, dedicated means of generating diverse populations. Since the VolEvol optimization problem can be difficult to formulate as an optimization problem across the entire search space, we so far relied on secondary means of generating diverse images. Some example in this regard are: using various mutation operators with tweaked parameters such that the resulting solution population exhibits some diversity; for multi-objective optimization, selecting solutions which are spread out across the determined Pareto front, in hopes that they would exhibit some level of variation in their characteristics. The same problem is intrinsically solved for MAP-Elites – type approaches, since it is often sufficient to select some of the elitist solutions from the resulting archive. With a carefully-constructed feature space, such solutions conform to the quality metrics used as optimization objectives which being naturally-diverse.

One important aspect with regard to the conducted research is that we did not find many (if any) papers which directly address the research questions of VolEvol. On the one hand, this means that there is potential for novel research in the direction addressed by the project. On the other hand, the scarcity of closely-matching previous work means that increased effort is required to come up with a solution to the addressed problem. However, we consider that the related work analysed by the VolEvol team and presented in this report adequately covers the relevant research conducted in our fields of interest. More importantly, this study has significantly contributed to our experience and understanding of applying evolutionary learning in the directions pursued by our project.

7 References

- [1] L. Wen, X. Wang, Z. Wu, M. Zhou, and J. S. Jin, "A novel statistical cerebrovascular segmentation algorithm with particle swarm optimization," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 148, pp. 569–577, 2015.
- [2] K. S. N. Ripon, L. E. Ali, S. Newaz, and J. Ma, "A multi-objective evolutionary algorithm for color image segmentation," in *Mining Intelligence and Knowledge Exploration*, Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 168–177, 2017.
- [3] Y. Bi, B. Xue, P. Mesejo, S. Cagnoni, and M. Zhang, "A survey on evolutionary computation for computer vision and image analysis: Past, present, and future trends," *IEEE Trans. Evol. Comput.*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 5–25, 2023.
- [4] W. M. Alobaidi and E. Sandgren, "An interactive evolutionary environment for creative design," *Mod. Mech. Eng.*, vol. 11, no. 02, pp. 27–51, 2021.
- [5] O. Parisot and T. Tamisier, "Applying genetic algorithm and image quality assessment for reproducible processing of low-light images," in *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Image Processing and Vision Engineering*, 2022.
- [6] S. Zhong, D. Berenson, and N. Fazeli, "CHSEL: Producing diverse plausible pose estimates from contact and free space data," in *Robotics: Science and Systems XIX*, 2023.
- [7] A. Gogna and A. Tayal, "Comparative analysis of evolutionary algorithms for image enhancement," *Int. J. Metaheuristics*, vol. 2, no. 1, p. 80, 2012.
- [8] Y. Zhou, C. Shi, B. Lai, and G. Jimenez, "Contrast enhancement of medical images using a new version of the World Cup Optimization algorithm," *Quant. Imaging Med. Surg.*, vol. 9, no. 9, pp. 1528–1547, 2019.
- [9] C. C. Gray, S. F. Al-Maliki, and F. P. Vidal, "Data exploration in evolutionary reconstruction of PET images," *Genet. Program. Evolvable Mach.*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 391–419, 2018.
- [10] Y. Jin, H. Wang, T. Chugh, D. Guo, and K. Miettinen, "Data-driven evolutionary optimization: An overview and case studies," *IEEE Trans. Evol. Comput.*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 442–458, 2019.
- [11] J. Marks et al., "Design Galleries: A General Approach to Setting Parameters for Computer Graphics and Animation," in *SIGGRAPH '97: Proceedings of the 24th annual conference on Computer graphics and interactive techniques*, New York, USA, 1997.
- [12] S. Chakraborty et al., "Differential Evolution and Its Applications in Image Processing Problems: A Comprehensive Review," *Computational Methods in Engineering*, vol. 30, p. 985–1040, 2023.
- [13] Z. A. Abbood, F. P. Vidal, "Fly4Arts : Evolutionary Digital Art with the Fly Algorithm," *Art and Science - ISTE OpenScience*, vol. 1, no. 1, 2017.
- [14] P. Ghamisi, J. A. Benediktsson, "Feature Selection Based on Hybridization of Genetic Algorithm and Particle," *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 309 - 313, 2015.
- [15] J. Kruse and A.M. Connor, "Multi-agent evolutionary systems for the generation of complex virtual worlds," *EAI Endorsed Transactions on Creative Technologies*, vol. 2, no. 5, 2015.
- [16] J. Zhang, C. Huang, Y. Huo, Z. Shi and T. Ma, "Multi-population cooperative evolution-based image segmentation algorithm for complex helical surface image," *Mathematical Biosciences and Engineering*, vol. 17, no. 6, p. 7544–7561, 2020.
- [17] L. Scarton and A. Hagg, "On the Suitability of Representations for Quality Diversity Optimization of Shapes," *Proceedings of the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference*, Jul. 2023.
- [18] N. Sankary and A. Ostfeld, "Stochastic Scenario Evaluation in Evolutionary Algorithms Used for Robust Scenario-Based Optimization," *Water Resources Research*, vol. 54, no. 4, pp. 2813–2833, Apr. 2018.
- [19] L.-L. Cai, B. P. Nguyen, C.-K. Chui, and S.-H. Ong, "Rule-Enhanced Transfer Function Generation for Medical Volume Visualization," *Computer Graphics Forum*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 121–130, Jun. 2015.
- [20] Z. Ali Abbood, J. Lavauzelle, É. Lutton, J.-M. Rocchisani, J. Louchet, and F. P. Vidal, "Voxelisation in the 3-D Fly Algorithm for PET," *Swarm and Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 36, pp. 91–105, Oct. 2017.

- [21] M. Raji, A. Hota, R. Sisneros, P. Messmer, and J. Huang, "Photo-guided exploration of volume data features", In Proceedings of the 17th Eurographics Symposium on Parallel Graphics and Visualization (PGV '17). Eurographics Association, Goslar, DEU, pp. 31–39, 2017.
- [22] K. Chatzilygeroudis, A. Cully, V. Vassiliades, and J.-B. Mouret, "Quality-Diversity Optimization: A Novel Branch of Stochastic Optimization," Springer Optimization and Its Applications, pp. 109–135, 2021.
- [23] J. Mouret, J. Clune. Illuminating search spaces by mapping elites. ArXiv, abs/1504.04909, 2015.
- [24] B. Tjanaka et al., "pyribs: A Bare-Bones Python Library for Quality Diversity Optimization," Proceedings of the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference, Jul. 2023.
- [25] V. Vassiliades, K. Chatzilygeroudis, and J.-B. Mouret, "A comparison of illumination algorithms in unbounded spaces," in Proceedings of the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference Companion, 2017.
- [26] M. Li and X. Yao, "Quality Evaluation of Solution Sets in Multiobjective Optimisation," ACM Computing Surveys, vol. 52, no. 2, pp. 1–38, Mar. 2019.
- [27] V. Vassiliades, K. Chatzilygeroudis, and J.-B. Mouret, "Using Centroidal Voronoi Tessellations to Scale Up the Multidimensional Archive of Phenotypic Elites Algorithm," IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 623–630, Aug. 2018.
- [28] A. Cully, "Multi-emitter MAP-Elites," Proceedings of the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference, Jun. 2021.
- [29] M. C. Fontaine, J. Togelius, S. Nikolaidis, and A. K. Hoover, "Covariance matrix adaptation for the rapid illumination of behavior space," Proceedings of the 2020 Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference, Jun. 2020.
- [30] J.-B. Mouret and G. Maguire, "Quality diversity for multi-task optimization," Proceedings of the 2020 Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference, Jun. 2020.
- [31] T. Pierrot, G. Richard, K. Beguir, and A. Cully, "Multi-objective quality diversity optimization," Proceedings of the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference, Jul. 2022.
- [32] L. Cazenille, "Comparing reliability of grid-based quality-diversity algorithms using artificial landscapes," in Proceedings of the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference Companion, 2019.
- [33] K. Sfikas, A. Liapis, and G. N. Yannakakis, "Controllable exploration of a design space via interactive quality diversity," in Proceedings of the Companion Conference on Genetic and Evolutionary Computation, 2023.
- [34] A. Gaier, A. Asteroth, and J.-B. Mouret, "Data-efficient design exploration through surrogate-Assisted Illumination," *Evol. Comput.*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 381–410, 2018.
- [35] A. Gaier, A. Asteroth, and J.-B. Mouret, "Data-efficient exploration, optimization, and modeling of diverse designs through surrogate-assisted illumination," in Proceedings of the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference, 2017.
- [36] M. Flageat and A. Cully, "Fast and stable MAP-Elites in noisy domains using deep grids," The 2020 Conference on Artificial Life, 2020.
- [37] A. Hagg, A. Asteroth, T. Bäck. Prototype Discovery Using Quality-Diversity. In: Auger, A., Fonseca, C., Lourenço, N., Machado, P., Paquete, L., Whitley, D. (eds) *Parallel Problem Solving from Nature – PPSN XV*. PPSN 2018. Lecture Notes in Computer Science(), vol 11101. Springer, Cham., 2018.
- [38] T. J. Choi and J. Togelius, "Self-referential quality diversity through differential MAP-Elites," Proceedings of the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference, Jun. 2021.
- [39] J. Lehman and K. O. Stanley, "Abandoning Objectives: Evolution Through the Search for Novelty Alone," *Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 189–223, Jun. 2011.
- [40] A. Hagg et al., "Expressivity of Parameterized and Data-driven Representations in Quality Diversity Search," in *GECCO 21*, Lille, France, 2021.
- [41] A. Hagg, "Hierarchical Surrogate Modeling for Illumination Algorithms," in *GECCO'17*, Berlin, Germany, 2017.
- [42] R. Boige et al., "Gradient-Informed Quality Diversity for the Illumination of Discrete Spaces," in *GECCO '23*, Lisbon, Portugal, 2023.

- [43] T. Wu, "Image-Guided Rendering with an Evolutionary Algorithm Based on Cloud Model," *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*, vol. 2018, pp. 1-19, 2018.
- [44] A. Alvarez, S. Dahlskog, J. Font, and J. Togelius, "Interactive Constrained MAP-Elites: Analysis and Evaluation of the Expressiveness of the Feature Dimensions," *IEEE Transactions on Games*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 202–211, Jun. 2022.
- [45] A. Alvarez, J. Font, "Learning the Designer's Preferences to Drive Evolution," in *International Conference on the Applications of Evolutionary Computation (Part of EvoStar)*, Seville, Spain, 2020.
- [46] S. Fioravanzo, G. Iacca, "MAP-Elites for Constrained Optimization," in *Constraint Handling in Metaheuristics and Applications*, Springer, 2021, pp. 151-173.
- [47] A. Hagg, A. Asteroth, T. Back, "Modeling User Selection in Quality Diversity," in *GECCO'19*, Prague, Czech Republic, 2019.
- [48] A. Cully and Y. Demiris, "Quality and Diversity Optimization: A Unifying Modular Framework," in *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 245-259, April 2018.

AI4media

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR
THE MEDIA AND SOCIETY

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 951911

info@ai4media.eu

www.ai4media.eu